

THE ROLE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN PROMOTION OF DOMESTIC TOURISM IN MOSHI RURAL, KILIMANJARO, TANZANIA

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*The authors declare
that no funding was
received for this work.*

Received: 02-April-2026

Accepted: 09-May-2026

Published: 22-May-2026

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This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (MSIJMR)** ISSN 3049-0669 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume 3 Special Issue 1, 2026

ABSTRACT: This study focuses on the role of local government in promoting domestic tourism in Moshi Rural. The general objective was to achieve the role of local government in promoting domestic tourism in Moshi Rural Tanzania. Specifically, study identified the contribution local government in promoting domestic tourism. The influence of community toward development of tourism and maintenance of their local sites. The study used a case study design because the describes the Role of Local Government in Promoting Domestic Tourism in Moshi Rural Kilimanjaro Tanzania. The study respondents were local respondents from local communities, local government leaders. And tourism officers. Both primary and secondary data was collected where questionnaires, interviewing key formats and observation methods were used in data location. SPSS and content analysis were used for data collection where information was summarized in frequency, percentage narratives and presented in table and figures.

Background of the Research Problem

While countries often tend to focus on international tourism due to the revenue earned through exports, domestic tourism

remains the leading form of tourism, representing an important tool for regional economic growth and development. With over 50% of the global population now categorised as middle class or rich, more and more people can afford to travel. An increasing number of households in emerging economies, which are approaching or have already reached these thresholds, including in China and India, are likely to contribute to sustained growth in domestic travel spending. In effect, in the next ten years an additional 65 million Chinese and 9 million Indians will enter the middle class Euromonitor's international (EI,2022).

The local government sector has traditionally played an important role in supporting tourism development of local areas. This included the provision of infrastructure, the development of tourist attractions and experiences, support for festivals and events and the implementation of tourist promotion plans. Tourism plans, policies and development objectives are core elements of the County and City Development Plans. Importantly, the sector mobilised a network of stakeholders including agencies, community groups and the private sector to invest in and promote their local tourist offering. These activities were driven by the ambition of each local authority to harness the development opportunity of areas throughout Ireland as places to live-in, invest in and visit in a sustainable way Euromonitor's international (EI,2016).

Travelling is generally perceived to be none essential across most African countries, as such many people do not engage in the activity. There has been less investment from most governments across the region to encourage travel amongst locals and limited competition in terms of airlines operating in most African markets. The cost of travel is generally very high in Africa in terms of transport and accommodation and therefore limited income often restricts frequency of travel. In sub-Saharan Africa domestic tourism is not developed compared to Europe continent this due to some reasons which include perceptions, whereby Perceptions play a great role in the influence of how Domestic Tourism in Sub-Saharan Africa grows. There is limited knowledge about availability of affordable accommodation options; as such people assume that travelling is only for high net-worth individuals. Across the region, there is generally Lack of a savings culture towards holiday travel amongst most Africans. Travelling is generally perceived to be none essential across most African countries.

Foreign visitors are perceived to have more spending power than locals; therefore, travelling is seen as not affordable in the eyes of locals (EI 2016).

Another key factor in Domestic Tourism in Sub-Saharan Africa is airlines. The region does not have many carriers and as such international airlines mainly operate in the region, taking a large chunk of the business. It is a very competitive industry as everyone is “rushing” for the little business – price is therefore a factor. Flights are expensive as the competitors are few and economic woes have resulted in quite a number of airlines shutting down or scaling back on routes.

In Tanzania domestic tourism is now an emerging opportunity compare to previous time. This is probably due to several campaign initiated by government to boost the sector for instance reduction of entrance fee to Tanzanian, massive awareness through the use of mass medias and promotions, Domestic arrivals accounts for about 48% in 2016 according to TANAPA statistics.

According to the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) in 2016, the Tanzanian domestic travel spending represents 30.2% of the direct contribution of Travel and Tourism to Tanzanian Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which was TZS 2,492 billion or 4.67% of the GDP in the year 2014. The domestic travel spending allowed the creation of 121,555 jobs in 2014, representing 1.15% of the total employment created in Tanzania for that year. According to WTTC, Tanzania’s domestic travel spending was TZS 752.5 billion in 2014 and is expected to growth by 6.1% by 2024 and generate 170,821 additional job.

Statement of the Research Problem

Tourism in Tanzania is regarded to be one among driving sectors of economy since 1990’s. The government and country at large is benefited In many aspect, both domestic tourism and international tourism are conducted in the Tanzania, but large emphasis are put on international tourism while the domestic tourist is seems to be ignored something which led the growth of these study, also under these circumstance we should consider the role of these domestic tourism toward the sources or tourism sites, by promoting domestic tourism will bust the current status of the environment, by considering different policies under the system for instance

Irresponsibility of some officials of local government in promoting domestic tourism has been a gravel concern in Moshi Rural in Tanzania. Various policies concerning promoting domestic tourisms in Tanzania has been issued and implemented for the purpose of improving people awareness about the nature of the tourist sites and their own refreshment (TANAPA, 2017). Looking forward in the document: CHAMA CHA MAPINDUZI (CCM) Policy of the year 2000 – 2010, the Government stated: The tourism sector appears to contribute a significant amount to the development of our National Income. In the next ten years we have to focus on improving tourism services both on the mainland and in Zanzibar and expanding our capacity to handle more tourists and increase revenues (CCM, 2010).

There is a need to design packages that will attract domestic tourists who should be enabled to enjoy the natural beauty of their country. There is also a need to improve access and develop strategies for Tanzanians to participate in the sector and provide services for tourists. The most attractive natural resources are those that are untouched. So, the effort to attract tourists should be accompanied by environmental protection measures for game parks, forests, beaches and lakes, all these put emphasize the international tourisms and doesn't consider the impact of domestic tourism the country.

Despite of having more benefit in our economy is necessary to understand how the local government participate in promotion and improve domestic tourism in their respective areas. The benefits associated with tourism growth in relation to economic development have to be analysed. Also, there is need to understand how local government is implementing those policies and regulation which are formulated in central government and ministry of tourism this is because of some reason firstly Kilimanjaro as a region or part of tourism is blessed with different tourist sites which in one way or another influence the mobility of tourist. Secondly tourism contribute much in economy of the nation from national level to community level since is the source of foreign exchange. This made the researcher to investigate the Role of Local Government in Promotion of Domestic Tourism in Moshi Rural in Kilimanjaro Tanzania.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

This research report seeks to achieve the role of local government in promoting domestic tourism in Moshi Rural Kilimanjaro, Tanzania.

Specific Objective

1. To determine the influence of local government in promoting domestic tourism in Moshi Rural, Kilimanjaro, Tanzania.
2. To assess the influence of local policies in maintaining the status of tourism in domestic sites which are located in Moshi Rural, Kilimanjaro, Tanzania.
3. To assess the role of individual leaders participates in the promotion on domestic sites in Moshi Rural, Kilimanjaro, Tanzania.

Research Questions

1. What were efforts of the local government in promoting tourism based on their local site's attraction in Moshi Rural, Kilimanjaro, Tanzania?
2. Was the local policy influence and maintain the status of the tourism in their communities?
3. Were the individual leaders, participate in promotion of local tourism sites in Moshi Rural, Kilimanjaro, Tanzania?

Significance of the Study

This study brings awareness to the ministry of Natural resources and tourism about the policies which has to be adopted so that will improve the status of local tourist sites.

the role of local government in promoting domestic in the community.

This study brings awareness to local leaders in local government in the best ways to conserve and ensure sustainability of this sites.

The stud

The domestic tourism was providing a way in which several pillars Moshi Rural benefited from the national to individual levels. For instance, in national level the government was increase its income hence the standard of social service and

infrastructure was improved, also in other hand Non-Government Organization and other stakeholders were benefited much from these study as the result that government will provide a room for free market competition and investment.

Where several stakeholders were invested in these types of tourism as a new economic opportunity. From these studies the community and individual improved in all aspect of life in the sense that through the collection of taxes in the community several services were Improved whilst in other hand individual get employment both directly (as the expert of tourism i.e., tour operators, guides, drivers.) and indirect (in hotels which host tourist, porters.)

Conceptual framework

Figure1.1 Conceptual Framework for Domestic Tourism, and the Role of Local Government

Source: Adapted from Paschal (2017)

Figure 1.1 shows the relationship between independent variables (roles of local government) and dependent variables (domestic tourisms). The local government through ministry of natural resources and tourisms have to formulate policies that favour and improve people interest in participating on domestic tourisms. However, this may depend on how tourist companies charge local people concerning domestic tourisms activities like transport fee, accommodation and meals. If the tourist company charge the same price that charges foreigners may leads to decrease number of local tourists. But if tourist company charges low price to local tourist may increase number of local tourists.

Local government set regulations for example regulation concerning environmental conservation that tourist have to follow them in order to conserve environment. The increase and decrease of local domestic tourisms depend on how they conserve environment in tourism sites. (Show positive impacts and negative impacts).

The diagram above demonstrates the relationship between variables and how each variable has a certain impact on the tourism industry.

For instance, local government through its attributes such as policies, regulation ad acts can lead to the increase or decrease of domestic tourism output. Also, intermediate variable (community) can affect the dependant variable (domestic tourism) if it will react positively or negatively.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Key Terms

Domestic Tourism can be described as tourism involving residents of one country travelling within their own country. It does not involve the crossing of international borders at entry points. As early recorded history provides a glimpse into ancient tourism activities, domestic tourism is in fact the first form of tourism practiced. It has been a well-established practice, happening in every country or region in the world. A strong relationship among tourism and visiting friends and relatives and religious pilgrimage has been found in countries with a long history of domestic tourism (Rogerson and Lisa, 2005).

Local Government can be defined as a sub-national, semiautonomous level government discharging its functions in specified area within a nation. By definition, Local Governments are the level of government that are closest to the people and therefore responsible for serving the political and material needs of people and communities at a specific local area. Such areas could be a rural setting or an urban setting, a village, a town, a suburb in a city or a city, depending on the size (URT,2016)

Table 2.1: Summary of Tourist Motivation Theories

Author (Year)	Theory Name	Citations (as of 18th Feb., 2018)	Contribution
Maslow (1943)	Hierarchy of needs Theory	23,831	-Explains that human behaviour is the outcome of various needs that occur in a hierarchal order and the fulfilment of one need leads to an awareness of the next level of need -Provides a better understanding of how human needs are a crucial underlying factor in any context
Dann (1977)	Push and pull theory of tourist motivation	1,662	-Builds a theoretical framework based on two concepts: anomie and eco-enhancement. - Defines the anomie factor as the desire to transcend feelings of isolation, while eco-enhancement derives from personal needs
Iso-Ahola (1982)	Social psychology model of tourism	1338	-Based on push and pull effects, asserts that personal escape and search and interpersonal escape and search motivate tourism and recreation -Combines the main elements (i.e. escape and reward) depending on the particular situation and tourists' goals

Empirical Review

Table 2.2.7 Empirical Summary

Author	year	Theme/context	strength	Weakness	Relevance
Ghimire	2006	-cooperation between regions to boost domestic tourism as well as regional tourism. -encourage people to visit their local destination as the way to participate and contribute economy of their countries.	It explains the importance and role of the people toward the domestic tourism and at the same time advice the government of respective region to formulate several alliances.	It does not put clear that how that region cooperation will bring positive impact on domestic tourism. Also, his methodologies were not familiar with the nature and customs of African societies	The article is relevance to my study since it reflects the research questions of what extent local government promote domestic destination hence it relate domestic tourism with contribution of government.
Zoleka	2005	-rapid population growth in developing countries and high economic growth among these countries can be used as an added advantage to uplift the status of domestic tourism.	It aiming at emphasizing the importance of available population to participate in tourism industry rather than waiting for international tourist.	Researcher does not include the status of economy between these developing countries due to the fact that not all developing countries have the same level of economy so it may implicate these estimations.	It assigns the role of individual or community in involvement or as the local tourist. Also, he defines the status of economy and how it affects tourism activities. the case study design used by researcher create bias in data

					collection and ignored poor one,
Bigano	2007	These often focus on domestic tourists of one country or in one region of a particular country the impacts of climate change on domestic tourism in developing countries.	He analyses the impact of climate change as the motivation factor.	Not all area is highly affected by climate change during tourism activities	He bases much on dependant variable and ignored the independent hence the result based on one side
UNWTO	2021	World report in domestic in each country in the world They identified statistic in each destination	This report helps to understand the status of domestic tourism in the country, also it can be used as the catalyst to the industry	The report does not consider the status and statistics of local tourist sites hence fail to provide an actual report.	This report is relevant to the study due to the fact that it provide the actual report which may used as an example.
UNWTO	2018	Highlights potential of domestic tourism to help to drive economic recovery in destinations world wide	Recognizing the importance of domestic tourism and its efforts in construction of economy.	Does not report about the pandemic (COVID-19) which affect the destination	It adds credibility on contribution in the domestic tourism
Batinoluho	2017	The development of	Discussed the status and	The study scope wa only in	it defined the various efforts

FL,		domestic tourism in secondary schools	development of domestic tourism in schools, it defined the various efforts which are undertaken by both local and central government in improving the industry	schools does not provide an insight on the community or other group participations in the industry	which are undertaken by both local government in improving the industry
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Luhanga	2014	Conducted a study on the opportunity of domestic tourism in the community	It explained the potentials which are provided by domestic tourism in the respective area and also the ways to maximize the positive outcomes	It has limited information concerning domestic tourism in the respective area	It is relevant to the study as it explained the potentials which are provided by domestic tourism Through sustainable development goals the conservation of environment is mentioned and domestic tourism depend much on quality of the environment.
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OECD	2016	Sustainable development goals as the business opportunity -the conservation of environment upgrades the quality of domestic tourism and hence it can help in development process.	It elaborated the essentials of investment and how they can be fulfilled in the presence of technology	It does not put emphasize on the influence of community as a opportunity to invest in tourism	
Author World Travels and Tourism council	year 2017	Theme/context Domestic tourism is the key driver of the tourism sector globally, accounting for 73% of total Travel & Tourism spending in 2017	Strength Highlighted the importance and economic impact of domestic tourism	Weakness it accounted the only the contribution in developed countries and few developing countries.	relevance it is relevant to the study as it explains how government consider the domestic tourism Governments use domestic tourism as a tool to eliminate local poverty, generate employment and economic growth, upgrade infrastructure and alleviate pressure from overcrowding through, for instance, discretionary pricing policies and the provision of non-wage tourism benefits.

Author	year	Theme /context	Strength	Weakness	Relevance
Danylo Gutsul	2018	Strategic Analysis of Domestic Tourism Development	The researcher proposed the ways which can be used to develop domestic tourism in the country	The study used a narrow scope in understanding the concept also derived examples from developed countries	The is study is relevant to my study as it explains Strategic efforts which can be used to develop domestic tourism

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Description of the Study Area

Location of the Study Area

Kilimanjaro is one of Tanzania's 31 administrative regions with a postcode number 25000. The regional capital is the municipality of Moshi. According to the 2012 national census, the region had a population of 1,640,087, which was lower than the pre-census projection of 1,702,207. For 2002-2012, the region's 1.8 percent average annual population growth rate was the 24th highest in the country. It was also the eighth most densely populated region with 124 people per square kilometre (United Republic of Tanzania, 2015) waterfalls). The region is bordered to the north and east by Kenya, to the south by the Tanga Region, to the southwest by the Manyara Region, and to the west by the Arusha Region.

United Republic of Tanzania (2019) Kilimanjaro region is located in the north east of Tanzania covering an area of 13209km². It is among the small regions in Tanzania which comprise about seven districts namely Rombo, Same, Mwanza, Hai, Moshi Rural, Moshi urban and Siha. It's a region which is surrounded with many tourist attractions such as water fall, national parks, forests and lakes without forgetting roof of Africa Mount Kilimanjaro.

The research will be conducted at Marangu east ward is one among the wards of Moshi rural with population of 23734 according to census of 2012. In three villages which are Kokirie, Ashira, Komalyango.

The Map of Kilimanjaro Region Showing Description of The Study Area.

Figure 3.1: The Map of Kilimanjaro Region and Study Villages

Source: United Republic of Tanzania

Research Design

A research design is the arrangement of the conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine the research purpose with economy in procedure (Kothari, 2009). This study used a case study design because the design describes the role of the local government in promoting domestic tourism in the respective area. Also, the study applied cross-sectional design, according to (De Vaus 2001) a cross-sectional survey refers to the collection of data from a sample of

individuals or groups at a particular point in time as a basis for inferring the characteristics of the population from which the sample comes from.

Population of the Study Area

This study was conducted in Marangu East ward which is very adjacent to Mountain Kilimanjaro. Its population according to the 2012 census was 23,734. where males are 11455 and females are 12279. Marangu east ward was formed east wards is formed by eight villages which are Lyamrakana, Lyasongoro, Ashira, Arisi, Samanga, Sembeti, Mshiri and Rauya (ward executive officer 2019)

However, the target villages of this study and three villages which was Lyamrakana with population of 3640 where males are 2362 and female 1278, Lyasongoro with population of 2567 where males are 975, and females 1592 Mshiri with 2567 population where males are 975 and females 1592 (National Bureau of statistics 2012). these village was selected due to their proximity to national parks, waterfall, and mountain Kilimanjaro where tourism activities are mostly conducted and also due to their special characteristics in relation with tourism.

Sampling Procedure and Techniques

Sampling is the process of obtaining information about an entire population by examining only a part of it (Kothari, 2004). The researcher used non probability sampling in choosing the villages that the study was undertaken. However, purposive and simple random sampling was adopted for getting sample required from the population in villages.

Sample Size

The study aimed to gain information on the role of local government in promoting domestic tourism in the areas with tourism the study used a sample size of 92 respondents, more specifically, the population of the study was made of 75 people from local community who were conducting and involving themselves directive in tourism activities. In addition to that 14 KINAPA officials, and local government leader was covered the respondents.

$$\frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Were

N=total population/population size

e=level of precision

n=sample size

The population of three selected areas is 9045 people given the house hold ratio as 3.0 the estimation of house hold will be shown as follows

Total household=total population/house hold ratio

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where by

n=sample size

N=total population

e=percentage of error rate at

100-90=10

$\frac{10\%=0.1}{100\%}$

100%

n=9045

$1+9045(0.1)^2$

N=98.9

Therefore, the sample size of the study area will be 99 respondents

Table 3.1 Overall Sample Size of the Targeted Population in the Study Area

S/N	Categories of Sample Size	Number of Sample size	Percentage (%) of Sample size	Sampling technique
1	Local communities	75	75.5%	Non snowball sampling
2	Tourism board officers	14%	14%	Purposive sampling
3	Village executive officer	3	3%	Purposive sampling
Total		99	100%	

Source: Own Construction (2025)

PRESENTATION OF THE FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

1.1 Age of Respondents

Age is an important demographic variable and is a primary basis of demographic classification in vital statistics, censuses and surveys.

Table 1.1: Age of Respondents (N=98)

Age	Frequency	Percentage%
15-19 years old	5	5.1
20-25 years old	37	37.8
26-30 years	28	28.6
35-40 years old	19	19.4
40-44 years	8	8.2
44-59 years	1	1.0
Total	98	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 4.1.1 presents age groups of respondents participating in community activities ranging from 15 to 59 and above. Results indicate that about 37(37.8%) of respondents in the study area were aged between 20-25 years followed by 28(28.6%) of the respondents aged 26-30 years. This finding is similar to Batinoluho (2017) who examined the development of domestic tourism in schools.

1.2 Gender of Respondents

Gender research covers different areas of specialization. Gender research is a term covering equality research, women's and feminist studies, research on men and queer studies. Figure 1.2 shows how men and women responded.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Figure 1.2 above shows the sex of respondents in the study area. Out of the 98 respondents interviewed, the highest proportion was females 56 respondents which were about (62%) and 23 respondents which are about (36%) which were male.

The field addresses basic issues such as democracy, equality and knowledge in society. Furthermore, it focuses on how gender interacts in conceptual and literal terms with other categories such as ethnicity, sexuality and social background.

Gender research elucidates the ways in which complex processes define gender and gender relations. This applies both to the often-unequal distribution of power between men and women and to the form of symbolic images that relate gender to

categories to which it has no obvious connection, such as nature and culture. All in all, gender research reveals how the perception of gender influences power and hierarchies in society.

These results are similar to what was observed by Timothy (2013) whereby in his findings he recognized that most of people involved in the production activities are females other than male, therefore the female is the one who propel the wheel of development un the community.

1.2 Marital Status of the Respondents

The respondents involved in this study comprised of different marital status. chart 4.1.2 shows the status of respondents from the communities if are married or are single but also those who are divorced and widowed.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Respondents were asked to state their marital status based on the option of whether they are single, married, separated, divorced or widowed. The findings shows that 55 respondents (46%) were married,40 respondents (44%) were single 8 respondents (4%) were widowed while separation (3%) and divorced were also (3%). The higher proportion of the single may suggest that there is high possibility of young people in

the societies as a sensor conducted in Tanzania shows that the high number of people found in Tanzania are youth and are the one responsible for tourism activities.

According to Nathalie (2016) drawing on focus group discussions and using logistic regression to analyse questionnaire data by compare the relative adoption of the different adaptive strategies of single, married, divorced and widowed men and women where she comes with the result of having larger number of people who are married.

1.3 Education Level

Education is the process of facilitating knowledge, skills, values morals beliefs and habits United Nations Educational, scientific and cultural organization (UNESCO 2021). Education is always valued as a means of deliverance from ignorance and enables one to perform effectively to any given task within a specified period. Respondents were asked to state their level of education. the table below shows the presentation of the education of respondents in **Figure 4.1.2 Education Level of Responses (N=98)**

Education level	Frequency	Percentage %
Primary	9	9.2
Ordinary Level	25	25.5
High level	25	25.5
Graduate	36	36.7
Others	2	2.0
Total	98	100

Source: Field Data Survey (2025)

Results in Fig. 1.3 indicate that the majority of the respondents have attended to different colleges were 36 respondents which were about (37%), while other attended to high level were 25 respondents which is about (26%), ordinary level were 25 respondents which is about (25%) primary and other level of the education were 2 respondents (1%). The results therefore suggest that the majority of community members had basic education and therefore likely to adopt new practices and ideas.

Most of the respondents in the study were therefore expected to be more helpful in emphasizing and promoting domestic tourism the results further reveal that the number of literacy level of the respondents (10%) with primary education is lower than the educated people, secondary o-level and A-level people also college and universities people.

According to UNICEF (2017), Tanzania achieved nearly universal access to primary education. However, since then, enrolment of primary school-aged children has been dropping. An estimated 2 million children between the ages of 7 and 13 years are out-of-school. Almost 70 per cent of children aged 14–17 years are not enrolled in secondary education while a mere 3.2 per cent are enrolled for the final two years of schooling.

Occupation

Actual physical possession or use of a dwelling or piece of land. Occupation exists only where it is recognizable as such, and where the occupant has a sufficient measure of control that prevents interference from strangers. The table below shows presentation

Occupation status

Activity	Frequency	Percentage%
Agriculture home stays operator	21	21.4
tourism employee	10	10.2
market works	18	18.4
shop owner	21	21.4
conservation workers transport provider	11	11.2
Government officials	7	7.1
Others	10	10.2
Total	98	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The Table 1.4 above shows that 21 respondents which are about (21.4%) were agriculturalist and shop owners, while 11 respondents were conservation workers transport provider which is about (11.2%) and 10 respondents deals with other occupation other than those mentioned (10.2%), this are people who are participating in tourism in a direct or indirect way such as tour transport provider, and tour guides, government officials were 7 respondents which is about (7.1%), other occupations which it was not mentioned in this study and was not related in one way or another constitutes about (10.2%.)

Gabriel (2018) reported that many people surrounding Moshi rural are participating in different activity and tourism is one of them. And according to him he explained that there is a need of different professions to participate in domestic tourism.

The role of Local Government in Promoting Domestic Tourism

This is one among the role of local government in promoting domestic tourism in Tanzania whereby the government has the role of providing enough information about the sites available in their area. One among its role is to provide better awareness in local sites.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Figure 1.5, The chart above shows the response of the community towards the local government efforts of ensuring the enough and right information is given to the community, whereby 50 respondents which were about (46.9%) strongly agreed, where 30 respondents which were about (40.8%) agreed the information that government has already them (6.1%) were un able to make decision about this fact may due to the enough knowledge concerning tourism, (5.1%) disagreed about this effort and they did not recognize those activities.

This show that majority of the community member are aware of this effort and only (13%) of the population does not understand. therefore, the government has the responsibility to make sure that the citizen is aware of this effort together their tourist at traction.

According to local government tourism policy people place, policies growing tourism to 2025 which was published in (2015), this policy aims at improving tourism to become one of largest leading industries in the countries.

Role Of Local Government in Providing High Quality to the Local Tourist

The table below shows the response of respondents towards the efforts of a local governments in providing quality service to the tourist as the means of promoting and maintaining the status of domestic tourism.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Fig 1.6, The chart above shows the influence of local government in promoting domestic tourism through ensuring high quality service to local tourist as a means of improving the industry,

from the field in which 20 respondents which is about (29.6%) strongly agreed about those efforts while 52 respondents which is about (48.0%) agreed and recognize those efforts,14.3% did not manage decisions about this question, 10 respondents which is about (6.1%) disagreed.

The influence of local government according to Zooleka (2004) refers to the efforts which are used by government and for this case is mainly a local government in improving the condition of our environment to be favourable for tourism activities. He also explained several efforts such as promotion of tourism site including those local sites in the community through advertisement by using several platforms such as SADEC, EAC.

5.1 Minimization of the Tax to Domestic Tourist

The chart below displays the efforts of local government in promoting domestic tourism through the minimization of additional tax to domestic tourist and domestic sites as the means of encouraging domestic tourism.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Figure 1.7: The chart above shows response of respondents towards the efforts of government in minimization of addition tax as the means of promoting domestic tourism whereby 45 respondents which is about (41.8%) strongly agreed that this will promote domestic tourism, while 35 respondents (39.8%) agreed, 10 respondents which is about 5 respondents which is about (9.2%) were un able to make decision they were not sure if this will be the best solution , 7 respondents which is about (7.1%) disagreed about these efforts as the way to encourage domestic tourist, and (2.0%) strongly disagree about this plan.

These findings are similar to the findings of (Luvinga 2010) who conducted research on the role of tourism in poverty alleviation of the community. Whereby he stated several efforts which government is taking in promoting tourism in those area which are adjacent to Mikumi National Park.

5.2 Improved Infrastructure in Tourist Sites

The process of improved infrastructure in tourist sites aimed at increasing and assuring the accessibility those destinations around the local area. The table below shows the response of citizen towards the efforts of local government in promoting domestic tourism.

Figure 4.5.2 **Source:** Field Survey (2025) The graph above displays the efforts of local government in improving infrastructure as a plan of promoting domestic tourism by ensuring accessibility to the destination.

Respondents' opinion from this perspective were as follows, 47 respondents which is about (38.8%) strongly agreed that has promoted and further will promote the industry, 35 respondents which is about (41.8%) agreed that to some extent this mechanism has managed to improve the industry, (9.2%) failed to make decision. (3.1%) disagree that won't change the scenario and (7.1%) strongly disagree about the action.

These findings are similar to those of World Travel and Tourism Council (2017), which explained on the importance and economic impact of domestic tourism in the economy of the both individual, community and national level.

5.3 The Motivation Toward Individuals to Domestic Tourism

Motivation means efforts which are used by local government to attract people to conduct their tourism activities in the respective area. The bar chart below shows the motivation towards the individuals' participation in domestic tourism.

Figure 1.9

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The bar graph above, provide discription of respondents views on the role of individual leaders in motivating and provide awareness about domestic tourism and local tourist sites, whereby 45 respondents they responses as (35.7%) strongly agree, 48 respondents which is about (38.8%)agreed that the local leaders are providing awareess on how to improve these industry,

10 respondents which is about (18.4%) they don't unnderstand realy if this awareness exist and therefore fail to make decision ,6.1% disagreed that the information provided is not sufficient to meet the current demand of promoting tourism.and 1.0% strongly disagreed.

These results are similar to Abubakar (2016) who analyzed the influence of the trust in a destiation and travel intention.motivation is one among the market techniquines to encourage people to participate in domestic tourism.

5.4 Existance of Good Policy in Maitaining Domestic Tourism

Policy is the course or principle of action adopted or proposed by an organization or individual.a policy is the statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or protocal althaus et al (2007).

These graphs and presentations below describe the influence of local policies in maintaining the status of tourism in domestic sites. this involved few questions as follows.

Source: Field Survey (2025)
Figure 5.7

The bar graph above displays the question of the existence of good policy from local government which create the suitable environment for tourist and their responses were as follows ,45 respondents which is about (43.9%) strongly agreed about the existence of those local policy in promoting domestic tourism, 40 respondents which is about (34.7%)agreed, while 5 respondents which is about (11.2%) were un able to decide fail to recognize,6.1% disagreed that there is no any policy exist related to the industry. And 4.1% strongly disagreed.

According to local government tourism policy people place, policies growing tourism to 2025 which was published in (2015), this policy aims at improving tourism to become one of largest leading industries in the countries.

5.8 The Local Government Officials give Enough Education about Tourism

Local government officials this are local government staffs which are working for the people in their localities, they are elected or selected by the government for example Ward Executive Officers and Village Executive Officers, all this leader is participating in different development activities, under this case these leaders are also responsible for providing awareness to the people in their areas.

The graph bellows shows the responses of people toward the role of local government officials in providing enough education about tourism.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Figure 5.9

The graph above explains the involvement of local government in providing enough education about tourism and particularly domestic tourism. Their responses were as follow, 45 respondents which is about (50.0%) agreed that the local government officials provide enough education concerning domestic tourism, 20 respondents which is about (30.6%) strongly agreed about this fact,8.2% were not make decision while (8.2%) disagreed and (2.0%) strongly disagreed.

These findings are similar to Gutsul (2018) who observed the similar results in the study on strategic development of domestic tourism.

5.9. This Policy Aims at Improving the Status of Domestic Tourism

Policy is the course or principle of action adopted or proposed by an organization or individual. A policy is the statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or protocol Althaus et al (2007).

The graph below shows the responses of those policy which are found in the local area and how they intend to improve the status of domestic tourism.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Here researcher aims was to found if this policy aiming at improving the domestic tourism, it happens sometimes the policy which are introduced are used in various sectors hence they fail to achieve expected goals, the response of this question was as follows, 60 respondents which is about (54.1%) agreed that this policy direct aims at improving domestic tourism, 30 respondents (29.6%) strongly agreed while 10 respondents which were (13.3%) fail to make decision, and about 5 respondents which is about (3.1%).

According to local government tourism policy people place, policies growing tourism to 2025 which was published in (2015), this policy aims at improving tourism to become one of largest leading industries in the countries.

4.6 Policies Implementation for a Change in Industry

The implementation of the policies seeks to achieve an oriented goal of individual or organisation’s domestic tourism policies of 2015 seek to develop the tourism industry to become a leading industry in Tanzania by 2025.the graph below shows the changes which were observed by respondents after the implementation of the policies.

Source: Field Survey (2025)

This question seeks to evaluate how far does these policies bring changes in the industry so that we can improve those area, respondent in this aspect respond as follow, 50 respondents which is about (49.0%) of population in the study agree that existence of this policies bring changes in the industry,

30 respondents which is about (28.6%) strongly agree,8 respondents (12.2%) this group fail to make decision, (8.2%) disagree about these changes which are brought by the policies. (2.0%) strongly disagreed,

This result is similar to Bigano (2007) who conducted a study on the domestic tourism whereby he observed the similar data in the aspect of policies.

REFERENCES

1. Akama J.S. and Sterry, P. (2006). *Cultural Tourism in Africa; Strategies for the New approach*. in J. S, new tourism. *Tourism Management* 23(1),17-26.
2. Andronicou, A. (1979). Tourism in Cyprus in de kadit (eds.) *Tourism-passport to Development?* Oxford University Press.294-318 *Achieve pro-poor Tourism Objectives*, progress in Developing studies,4. (4);
3. BOT, MNRT, NBS, IMMIGRATION DEPT, ZCT; *Tanzania Tourism Sector SurveyReports*; 2001, 2004, 2005, 2006 and 2007,2008
4. Britton, S. G. (1982). *The political economy of tourism in the Third World. Annals of Tourism Research*.Vol.9. Iss, 3. Pg. 331–58 (Berk and DeMarzo, 2007;Perks, 2007; Atril and McLaney, 2008).
5. Lew, A. (2008) *Tourism is not the world's largest industry -- so stop saying it is*[Online] Available at:[http://tourismplace.blogspotl.com/2008/04/tourism-is-not-worlds largest industry.html](http://tourismplace.blogspotl.com/2008/04/tourism-is-not-worlds-largest-industry.html) Accessed: 28 October 2000 Mainland Tanzania andZanzibar.
6. Maslow, A. H. (1969a). *The farther reaches of human nature*. *Journal of Transpersonal Psychology*,1(1), 1–9.

7. Maslow, Abraham H. (1993). "Theory Z". In Abraham H. Maslow, *The farther reaches of human nature* (pp. 270–286). New York: Arkana (first published Viking, 1971). Reprinted from *Journal of Transpersonal Psychology*, 1969, 1(2), 31–47.
8. Ndunguru, P.C. (2007). *Lectures on Research Methodology for Social Sciences*, New Age International Publishers. New Delhi. New Age International (P)Limited, Publishers.
9. Odhiambo, N.M. (2010b), *Energy Consumption, Prices and Economic Growth in Three SSA Countries: A Comparative Study*. *Energy Policy* 38: 2463-2469 *Review*, 14(4), 532-550. *e-Review of Tourism Research (eRTR)*, Vol.9, No. 3, 2011
10. TANAPA. (2008). "*Tanzania National parks*." Retrieved 15/04, 2008.
11. U.R.T. (2002). *Integrated Tourism Master Plan for Tanzania: Strategy and Actions*
12. World Bank Group (2006). *Attracting Investment in Tourism*. [Online] Available from www.fdipromotion.com/toolkit/Documents/1/Tanzania.pdf. [Accessed on 20th May 2009]